

Signal analysis from Multi-Photomultiplier detectors in Water Cherenkov Test Experiment (WCTE)

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Hyper-Kamiokande (HK)

The **Hyper-Kamiokande** is a next-generation water Cherenkov neutrino detector located about 300 km from the J-PARC neutrino source. It consists of a cylindrical tank (71 m high, 68 m diameter) containing ~258 kt of ultra-pure water, corresponding to a fiducial volume 8.4 times larger than Super-Kamiokande.

The detector is instrumented with ~20,000 high-QE 0.5 m PMTs and ~800 mPMTs.

Its physics goals include precision measurements of CP violation, searches for proton decay, and observations of neutrinos from supernovae, among other neutrino and astroparticle physics studies.

Hyper-Kamiokande detector concept

Intermediate Water Cherenkov Detector (IWCD)

The **Intermediate Water Cherenkov Detector** is a water Cherenkov detector approximately 8 m tall and 10 m in diameter, located about 800 m from the beam exit. It measures the unoscillated neutrino beam flux and interaction cross sections. The detector is equipped with 360 mPMT modules, and its adjustable water level allows the vertical position to vary the off-axis angle from 1.5° to 4°.

IWCD detector concept

Water Cherenkov Test Experiment (WCTE)

The **Water Cherenkov Test Experiment (WCTE)** was a 30-ton water Cherenkov detector at CERN, measuring 3.8 m in height and 3.6 m in diameter. It was instrumented with 93 IWCD-style mPMTs, 4 HK-style mPMTs, 8 internal cameras, and a mounted light-pulsar system with fast LEDs.

WCTE operated from autumn 2024 to summer 2025, exposed to π^+ , μ^+ , e^+ , and protons with momenta between 100 and 1200 MeV/c. The detector primarily ran in ultra-pure water, with a short (1.5-week) gadolinium-loaded water campaign.

WCTE interior

Multi-Photomultiplier Detector System (mPMT)

Each **multi-PMT module (mPMT)** integrates 19 × 8 cm (3") Hamamatsu R14374 PMTs, providing improved granularity and timing compared to large-area PMTs, with a timing resolution better than 1 ns. The PMTs use Cockcroft-Walton HV bases and are housed in a watertight vessel with integrated front-end electronics. An acrylic dome filled with silicone gel and anodised reflectors increases the effective active area.

PMT signals are digitized as waveforms with 8 ns sampling. Pulse arrival times are reconstructed using a digital constant fraction discriminator (CFD).

Calibration is performed using an integrated light-pulsar system with fast LEDs (365, 405, 470 nm) delivering light via optical fibres with diffusers or collimators for precise timing and gain calibration.

Multi-PMT scheme

Example waveform from mPMT channel

WCTE Data Analysis - Motivation

Key studies in WCTE: e/μ separation, π^0 -related e/γ discrimination, water-target response, measurements of detector response to μ of similar momenta, and exploring a path toward $\nu/\bar{\nu}$ tagging via neutron capture on gadolinium.

This work is a preliminary analysis which aims to develop tools for WCTE beam data studies that do not rely on a full event reconstruction.

WCTE event display examples for different particles

Analysis of signal from muons of similar momenta

Average event display from muons of different momenta

1. Sector-based analysis: The detector is divided into sectors to identify signal asymmetry.

The detector is divided into sectors (top, bottom, left, and right). Splitting the muon ring signal into sectors allows identification of asymmetries in different regions of the detector. Sector charge histograms are normalized by the number of active mPMTs to account for variations in detector coverage.

PMTs charge distributions in different sectors

WCTE detector divided into sectors

2. Row/column analysis: The signal is studied across different mPMTs grouped in rows and columns of the detector.

The detector signal is analyzed across rows and columns formed by grouping mPMTs accordingly. Studying the signal in each group enables **characterization of Cherenkov ring profiles**. Gaussian fits to these profiles for different muon momenta are used to estimate differences in the detector response.

Gaussian fit to ring profiles from muons of different momenta

3. Ring fitting: Cherenkov ring is fitted with motivation to obtain ring width.

The width of the Cherenkov ring is estimated by fitting a circular model to the observed light pattern, assuming the ring plane to be perpendicular to the particle direction. The distances between the fitted ring and the detected photon signals are then evaluated, and their spread is quantified using the standard deviation of this distance distribution. This standard deviation is taken as a measure of the Cherenkov ring width, and its distribution for all muon events in a given run is shown below.

Distribution of σ obtained from Cherenkov ring fitting

Conclusion

This work presents a preliminary study of the mPMT response to beams of known particles in WCTE, without applying efficiency corrections. The analysis demonstrates that detector non-uniformities, Cherenkov ring profiles, and ring widths can be studied using mPMT information, without relying on the standard event reconstruction.